

PRACTICE OF VISUAL DIAGNOSTICS USING ENDOSCOPES**Yuriy Saliy***Assistant**Kharkiv National Automobile and Highway University***Nikita Petrushev***Bachelor student**Kharkiv National Automobile and Highway University***Nalia Penkina***Lecturer at the automotive and mechanical department of**Kharkiv State Automobile and Food Processing University, Kharkiv, Ukraine***Igor Pimonov***Candidate of Technical Sciences, Head of the Department of Operation, Testing,**Service of Construction and Road Machines**Kharkiv National Automobile and Road University***Abstract**

Repair of machinery begins with visual inspection during maintenance of mechanical equipment and ends with visual confirmation of detected defects during repair. The subjectivity of this method of technical diagnostics is compensated by the possibility of training specialists in various directions: in current inspection, in defect analysis, in determining the causes of damage, in non-destructive testing, etc. The peculiarities of human vision should be taken into account. It is necessary to take into account peculiarities of human vision, quality of illumination, used optical devices, disregard illusions and many other things. Visual inspection begins with the development of an algorithm and formulation of signs of damage to the mechanism elements, approaches to the identification of types of mechanical wear. There are peculiarities for visual inspection when used in nondestructive testing methods. The article considers the main provisions of visual diagnostics used in the inspection of mechanical equipment, which leads to an increase in the efficiency of working processes of construction and road machines due to the automation of observation processes.

Keywords: operation, automation, visual inspection, efficiency, construction and road vehicles.

When working with mechanical equipment, it is often necessary to inspect the most remote parts and assemblies closed by the housing without disassembling the mechanism. This occurs when inspecting the mechanism before repair, when performing adjustment operations or after repair to control the completeness of the components, and in other cases. The first stage of endoscopes (endon - inside and skopeo - to examine) was associated with the use of mirrors and portable small-sized light sources. The second stage was associated with the development of fiber-optic technologies and light sources with a high degree of illumination, which was implemented in the designs of boroscopes and fibroscopes. The third stage began with the advent of video endoscopes.

The types of defects that are detected vary depending on the purpose of the machine or assembly: cracks, chipping, scoring, burn-throughs and deposits

on parts, cavities, corrosion, coating defects, adhesions, wear of friction surfaces, correct positioning of parts, integrity of internal fasteners, foreign objects in internal cavities, contaminant deposits, foreign object scratches on internal machine parts, etc. The minimum size of surface defects detected by endoscopes is, in some cases, up to 0.02 mm, and defects as small as 0.15 mm can be measured and documented on digital media. The difficulty of defect detection is associated with the limited field of view, a specialist can see only a part of the defect that needs to be identified and the degree of danger determined. There are no guarantees of inspection of the entire controlled area of the object. Examples of faults recorded during inspection with an endoscope are shown in Figure 1. Inspection of complex technical facilities should be preceded by a methodical study of the sequence of work.

Fig. 1. Examples of images obtained with a video endoscope during the inspection of various inspection objects

Undoubtedly, the high qualification of the endoscopist is essential for determining an objective picture of the technical condition of the product, but the quality of the image generated by the endoscope largely determines the probability of detecting defects, the speed of inspection and the reliability of the diagnostic results. Often, when working with a damaged endoscope, some defects simply "fall out of sight."

The experience of using technical endoscopes has made it possible to formulate the main rule of effective use - the parameters of the endoscope must be appropriate for the task. When using endoscopes, the field of view is narrowed, so you should first answer the question of what you expect to see in the dark and to what smallest detail this object should be examined.

The basis of the endoscope is an optical system consisting of a working part with optical fibers, lenses, or a video camera, through which the image is transmitted from the object to the eyepiece or screen of the device. To make the image visible, the object under study must be illuminated. For this purpose, a lighting system is used - an illuminator with a light source and

a light guide cable for transmitting light from the illuminator to the object or LED light sources.

Rigid endoscopes (boroscopes) are designed for visual inspection of components that can be accessed directly. Boroscopes provide a higher quality image and are used to inspect the cavities of machines and mechanisms, small-diameter channels and pipes, casting cavities, and ground and honed holes. A boroscope consists of an optical and lighting system (Figure 4.29). The optical system consists of lens, rod, or gradient optics enclosed in a metal tube. The illumination system consists of an optical fiber that is located between the outer and inner metal tubes. The light source (mercury or halogen lamp) with a reflective system and ventilation system is located separately at a distance of 1...2 m from the observer. Boroscopes are characterized by the diameter and length of the working part, the angle of observation and the angle of the field of view. Circular view boroscopes allow for 360° viewing without moving the instrument body. Some models have a variable field of view and viewing direction. Viewing eyepiece includes focus and sharpness adjustment

Fig. 2 - Schematic of a boroscope: 1 - illumination lens; FOV - field of view angle; DOF - direction of view; 2 - objective; 3 - lenses; 4 - light guide; 5 - system of rotation of the observation tube; 6 - connection of the light guide tip; 7 - eyepiece; 8 - focus adjustment ring; 9 - visual acuity adjustment ring

The diameter of the working part is 2...10 mm. The length of the boroscopes is 100...1000 mm. Main angles of observation direction: 0°, 30°, 45°, 75°, 90°, 120°. The viewing angle is fixed by using interchangeable lenses - 30°, 45°, 90°, 120°. There are boroscopes with

a wobbly prism that smoothly change the viewing direction in the range of 55°...115°. Depending on the purpose of the inspection, the field of view can be narrow 35°, medium 60° or wide 90°.

Fig. 3. General view of a boroscope

Flexible endoscopes (fiberscopes, see Figure 3) - are used in cases where direct access to the object is impossible or the object has a complex shape. In fiberscopes, the visual and light transmission systems consist of fiber optics located inside a flexible tube. An optical light guide connects the lens objective and the

eyepiece. The illumination system includes a light-diffusing lens that illuminates the object, a fiber optic harness, and a special tip that connects to the illuminator. Standard light sources with xenon, halogen or ultraviolet lamps are used as illuminators.

Fig. 3. General structure of the fiberscope:

RO - viewing sector; *DOT* - angle of rotation of the distal end; 1 - objective lens; 2 - end of the illuminating light guide; 3 - eyepiece; 4 - light guide; 5 - focus adjustment ring; 6 - visual acuity adjustment ring; 7 - control of the distal end rotation to the right and left; 8 - controlling the rotation of the distal end up and down

Typically, a video endoscope has a semi-rigid fiber optic cable, at the end of which there is a video camera that transmits the image to the endoscope monitor and LEDs for illumination. One of the issues is to protect the camera from water and aggressive media (oils, gasoline, antifreeze, etc.).

Improvement of video endoscope designs is aimed at increasing the resolution of cameras, reducing their size, and using special USB extenders that allow to observe the image from a distance of up to 8...10 m.

Multi-zone illumination of the investigated part of the structure with the help of miniature LEDs (their number in modern devices can be 6 or more) ensures the clarity of the color picture (Figure 4). Portable video cameras, a connecting wire, and a plug for connecting to the USB port of a desktop computer, laptop, or telephone are becoming widespread. You can use the tools of the operating system or apply specialized application software.

Fig. 4. Video endoscopes

The advantages of video endoscopes are based on the use of digital technologies: high resolution; increased viewing angle and image scale; image storage and saving, measurement of distance to the object and size of lesions, image editing and analysis, the ability to use expert systems, audio and text comments, image separation and overlay, etc. The use of special programs can significantly improve the quality of the image. As a result of the use of boroscopes and fiberscopes in the inspection of mechanical equipment, two groups have emerged. Professionals - for whom the endoscope is the main element of the inspection process. Specialists - use the endoscope periodically, not systematically.

The use of endoscopy in conjunction with other non-destructive testing methods makes it possible to identify diagnostic results obtained by ultrasonic, eddy current, radiographic, vibroacoustic, acoustic emission, metallographic, thermal imaging and other non-destructive testing methods in case of difficult access to the tested assembly.

"It's better to see once (without special disassembly of the unit) than to hear a hundred times." The high qualification of the endoscopic inspector is crucial for determining an objective picture of the technical condition of the product. It should also be noted that the quality of the image produced by the endoscope largely determines the probability of detecting defects, the speed of inspection, and the reliability of diagnostics in general. Thus, the reliability of defect detection is determined by the characteristics of the device used, selected for the selected object of control.

The smaller the diameter of the endoscope (4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 8.0, 10.0 mm...), the smaller the opening for inserting the device into the object of study, but the outer diameter should be smaller than the diameter of the opening. If the diameter of the endoscope is smaller than the diameter of the working hole, there are additional opportunities for movement and increase of the viewing area when changing the angle of inclination and turning. When using a small diameter endoscope, the effective inspection area is reduced, inspection time is increased, eye fatigue is increased, and the probability of error (missed or false detection of a defect) is increased. For inspections through small,

medium, and large openings, it is best to use two sizes. To obtain a clear image with a video endoscope recorded online to a memory source, it is necessary to use a matrix with a resolution of at least 640×640 pixels.

The length of the endoscope should be appropriate for the size of the object. At maximum immersion, the outer part of the endoscope should not be too long. For boroscopes, the length can be up to 300 diameters. The maximum length of a boroscope is 4200 mm. Fiberscopes can have a length of up to 670 working diameters. The standard length of a fiberscope is 3 meters. The length of a semi-rigid video endoscope usually does not exceed 700 mm. There are probes with a diameter of 6.1 mm and a length of up to 18 m and a diameter of 10 mm and a length of up to 30.5 m. In the case of a variety of objects to be inspected, you should not focus on the largest dimensions, but form groups of objects that are unified in size for inspection. The image quality does not depend on the length; with a long endoscope length, it is certainly possible to examine small objects, but not conveniently. Autofocus - as a rule, the camera built into the video endoscope automatically focuses 1...6 centimeters from the object.

The viewing angle (0°, 45°, 70°, 90°, 110° - the angle from the endoscope axis to the center of the viewing area) should correspond to the task at hand - searching for defects located on the side surface or in the direction of direct viewing. If the object of inspection is located in a straight line from the insertion point, the angle of the inspection direction is set to 0°. If the object of inspection is located close to the point of entry, for example, engine injectors near the spark plug holes, the inspection angle should be 120°. When inspecting the walls of pipelines, a side view of 90° is used. Lighting - to inspect an object, illumination of 1000...2000 lux is required. This is achieved with fiber optic lighting, in which fiberglass transmits light from an external light source through flexible light guides to the lens, or with LED illuminators installed next to the video camera. A dimming function is desirable, as glare can be a problem when inspecting polished surfaces, making it difficult to see.

Measurements using the comparison method are based on the dimensions of a known object in the field of view or placed in the viewing area. The accuracy of

the measurement depends on the operator's ability to assess the quality of the image and on his/her ability to place the measuring cursors.

Controlling the endoscope presents some difficulties at the initial stage of mastering the device - it is necessary to coordinate the movement of the lens or camera with the movements of the hands. Skills are acquired relatively quickly, but also quickly forgotten. Therefore, the inspection performed after a break increases in duration.

Obtaining a high-quality image Image quality requires some skill in holding the device and operating the probe. You will not be able to see a high-quality image with shaking hands.

Maintenance includes cleaning of optics (lenses) and endoscope elements with a cotton cloth moistened with glass cleaner or 70% aqueous alcohol solution. Do not use cleaning solutions.

To prevent injury during operation and to avoid damage to the endoscope, read the instructions for use of the endoscope, the instructions for use of the illuminator and power supply, and observe the restrictions for use. It is prohibited to use of the endoscope for examination of equipment under voltage or in operating mechanisms;

sharp ($R \leq 70$ mm) bends of the endoscope working part;

look towards the light flux emitted by the illuminator;

touch the illuminator and power supply with wet hands;

step on the working part or the light guide cable;

strike the working part against hard objects and contact with sharp edges;

drop the endoscope, its parts and components.

Immerse the endoscope in water, wash it under running water; apply excessive force, sudden movements during operation, when inserting and removing the working part, when putting the endoscope in the case; use the device in explosive atmospheres.

The advantages of using endoscopes are primarily related to the use of the information obtained. Visual fixation of the presence or absence of defects, obtained without disassembling the mechanism, allows you to make informed decisions about the timing and scope of

planned repairs. Illumination of the inspected surface with a beam of light creates conditions for involuntary concentration of attention on a small area of the surface. The combination of an endoscope with a computer, photo and video recording makes it possible to save the images and data obtained for further analysis.

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